

THE ROLE OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF IDA IN PREPARATION FOR PREGNANCY

Rajabova Oygul Islomovna

Asian International University.

oygul.islomovna.1997@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15494058>

Abstract. IDA is one of the most common diseases during pregnancy and the postpartum period. Statistical analysis of the study showed that many obstetric complications, such as polyhydramnios, chronic renal failure, intrauterine growth restriction, premature birth, weak labor, perineal ruptures, lochiometra, more often developed in women with IDA who did not prepare for pregnancy. Women with insufficient protein nutrition, with heavy menstruation for more than 7 days, multiparous women, women with chronic infectious diseases or chronic diseases of internal organs (in particular, the gastrointestinal tract), pregnant women with multiple pregnancies and / or having a short period of time between births belong to the group with high risk factors for the development of IDA. This article describes the role of IDA diagnosis and treatment in preparing for pregnancy.

Keywords: pregnancy, polyhydramnios, lochiometra, chronic diseases, anemia, tachypnea, gastrointestinal tract, menstruation, chronic renal failure.

Relevance. The prevalence of IDA is staggering: 2 billion people, or more than 30% of the world's population, suffer from anemia, many due to iron deficiency (about 20%). Of these, according to WHO estimates, 42% of children under five and 40% of pregnant women worldwide suffer from IDA. In terms of frequency, direct and indirect impact on maternal and perinatal mortality, anemia remains important for public health worldwide. About 30% of all women of reproductive age already have latent iron deficiency before pregnancy due to various etiologies.

The aim of the study is to evaluate the role of IDA diagnostics and treatment at the stage of preparation for pregnancy as a prevention of complications of pregnancy and childbirth.

Materials and methods of the study. 59 women from the postpartum department of the 2nd maternity hospital in Bukhara aged 18 to 42 years were examined. Based on the data of the delivery history and the survey, the following were identified: the first group - 40 women admitted for delivery with IDA of varying severity; the second group - 19 women who were admitted without anemia, but they were treated in preparation for pregnancy. Statistical analysis was performed in Microsoft Excel. Results and discussion: Among the patients of the first group, the following were significantly more common: polyhydramnios in 5 women (12.5%), chronic fetal renal failure in 3 women (7.5%), fetal hypoxia in 7 women (17.5%), grade 1 IUGR in 4 women (10%), and threatened miscarriage in 12 women (30%) than in the second group. Premature labor (15%), primary and secondary weakness of labor (20%), grade 1–2 perineal ruptures (10%), and lochiometra (7.5%) were also significantly more common among the patients of the first group. When assessing the condition of newborn children of women in the study groups, it was found that cases of transient tachypnea with the development of grade 1 and 2 iron deficiency anemia (15%) were more common in children born to mothers in the first group compared to the second. During the study of the medical histories of women in the two study groups, the most common factors that can lead to iron deficiency were identified, which were also more common among patients in the first group: insufficient protein nutrition - 20.3%,

heavy menstruation for more than 7 days - 25.4%, chronic infectious diseases or chronic diseases of internal organs (in particular, the gastrointestinal tract) - 13.6%, multiple births and / or a short period of time between births - 32.2%, menstrual irregularities - 8.5%. **Conclusions:** Detection and effective treatment of IDA at the stage of preparation for pregnancy significantly reduces the incidence of complications during pregnancy and childbirth. Identification of risk factors for the development of IDA will allow timely diagnosis of latent iron deficiency and prevent the development of IDA.

REFERENCES

1. Islomovna, R. O. (2024). VIRUSLI GEPATITLAR VA TUG 'RUQDAN KEYINGI ERTA QON KETISHLARNI KAMAYTIRISHNING YANGI TEXNOLOGIYALARI. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 39(5), 99-106.
2. Islomovna, R. O. (2024). A Comparative Analysis of the Effectiveness of Vaginal Progesterone, Cervical Pesar, and Their Combination for Preventing the Risk of Premature Labor in High-Risk Pregnant Women *BEST JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN SCIENCE. RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT*, 3(3), 440-446.
3. Islomovna, R. O. TACTICS FOR CARRYING WOMEN AT HIGH RISK OF RECURRENT MISCARRIAGE.
4. Islomovna, R. O. OPTIMIZING THE CHOICE OF HORMONAL CONTRACEPTION IN WOMEN WITH AUTOIMMUNE THYROIDITIS DISEASE.
5. Islomovna, R. O. CHARACTERISTICS OF UROGENITAL TRACT MICROBIOCENOSIS IN WOMEN WITH NON-DEVELOPING PREGNANCY.
6. Rajabova, O. I. (2024). Method Stopping Atonic Bleeding From the Uterus after Childbirth Using Balloon Tamponade. *International Journal of Alternative and Contemporary Therapy*, 2(9), 107-110
7. Islomovna, R. O. (2024). METHODS OF PHARMACOTHERAPEUTIC TREATMENT OF ABNORMAL UTERINE BLEEDING IN GIRLS. *PEDAGOGIKA, PSIXOLOGIYA VA IJTIMOYIY TADQIQOTLAR/ JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGY, PSYCHOLOGY AND SOCIAL RESEARCH*, 3(5), 192-197.
8. Islomovna, R. O. (2024). MODERN CONCEPT OF RECURRENT VAGINAL INFECTIONS IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE. *JOURNAL OF HEALTHCARE AND LIFE-SCIENCE RESEARCH*, 3(4), 128-131.
9. Rajabova, O. (2025). DIAGNOSTICS AND TREATMENT OF CERVICAL INTRAEPITHELIAL NEOPLASIA IN PREGNANT WOMEN. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(2), 996-1000.
10. Jo'rayeva, G. (2024). COMBINATION OF DIABETES AND METABOLIC SYNDROME. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12), 691-696.
11. Jo'rayeva, G. (2025). RISK FACTORS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CLIMACTERIC DISORDERS IN WOMEN WITH THE METABOLIC SYNDROME. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 1090-1092.
12. Jo'rayeva, G. (2025). THE ROLE OF THYROID HORMONES IN CHILD DEVELOPMENT. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(2), 990-995.
13. Jo'rayeva, G. (2025). CALCIUM METABOLISM AND OSTEOPOROSIS: THE ROLE OF THE ENDOCRINE SYSTEM. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(3), 1155-1159.

14. Халимова, Ю. С. (2021). MORPHOFUNCTIONAL ASPECTS OF THE HUMAN BODY IN THE ABUSE OF ENERGY DRINKS. *Новый день в медицине*, 5(37), 208-210.
15. Халимова, Ю. С. (2022). МОРФОФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ЯИЧНИКОВ КРЫС ПРИ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИИ КОФЕИН СОДЕРЖАЩИХ НАПИТКОВ. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 23, 368-374.
16. Salokhiddinovna, X. Y. (2023). INFLUENCE OF EXTERNAL FACTORS ON THE MALE REPRODUCTIVE SYSTEM. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 3(10), 6-13.
17. Халимова, Ю. С., & Шокиров, Б. С. (2022). МОРФОФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ВНУТРЕННИХ ОРГАНОВ ПРИ ХРОНИЧЕСКОМ АЛКОГОЛИЗМЕ. *Scientific progress*, 3(2), 782-789.
18. Halimova, Y. S. (2023). Morphological Aspects of Rat Ovaries When Exposed to Caffeine Containing Drink. *BEST JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN SCIENCE, RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT*, 2(6), 294-300.
19. Halimova, Y. S., Shokirov, B. S., & Khasanova, D. A. (2023). Reproduction and Viability of Female Rat Offspring When Exposed To Ethanol. *Procedia of Engineering and Medical Sciences*, 32-35.
20. Salokhiddinovna, H. Y. (2023). Morphological Features of the Human Body in Energy Drink Abuse. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 3(5), 51-53.
21. Халимова, Ю. С., & Шокиров, Б. С. (2022). СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ДАННЫЕ О МОРФОФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ АСПЕКТАХ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО ОРГАНИЗМА ПРИ ЗЛОУПОТРЕБЛЕНИЕ ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКИМИ НАПИТКАМИ. *PEDAGOGS journali*, 4(1), 154-161.
22. Halimova, Y. S. (2023). Morphofunctional Aspects of Internal Organs in Chronic Alcoholism. *AMALIY VA TIBBIYOT FANLARI ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(5), 83-87.
23. Shokirov, B. S. (2021). Halimova Yu. S. Antibiotic-induced rat gut microbiota dysbiosis and salmonella resistance Society and innovations.
24. Халимова, Ю. С., & Шокиров, Б. С. (2021). Репродуктивность и жизнеспособность потомства самок крыс при различной длительности воздействия этанола. In *Актуальные вопросы современной медицинской науки и здравоохранения: Материалы VI Международной научно-практической конференции молодых учёных и студентов, посвященной году науки и технологий, (Екатеринбург, 8-9 апреля 2021): в 3-х т.*. Федеральное государственное бюджетное образовательное учреждение высшего образования «Уральский государственный медицинский университет» Министерства здравоохранения Российской Федерации.
25. Khalimova, Y. S. BS Shokirov Morphological changes of internal organs in chronic alcoholism. *Middle European scientific bulletin*, 12-2021.
26. Шокиров, Б. С., & Халимова, Ю. С. (2022). ДИСБИОЗ ВЫЗВАННЫЙ АНИБИОТИКАМИ КИШЕЧНОЙ МИКРОБИОТЫ КРЫС И УСТОЙЧИВОСТЬ К САЛМОНЕЛЛАМ. *Scientific progress*, 3(2), 766-772.
27. Salokhiddinovna, X. Y. (2023). Clinical Features of the Course of Vitamin D Deficiency in Women of Reproductive Age. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 3(11), 28-31.

28. Шокиров, Б., & Халимова, Ю. (2021). Антибиотик-индуцированный дисбиоз микробиоты кишечника крыс и резистентность к сальмонеллам. *Общество и инновации*, 2(4/S), 93-100.
29. Salokhiddinovna, X. Y. (2023). MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN PATHOLOGICAL FORMS OF ERYTHROCYTES. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 3(11), 20-24.
30. Saloxiddinovna, X. Y. (2023). ERITROTSITLAR PATOLOGIK SHAKLLARINING MORFOLOGIK O'ZGARISHLARI. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 33(1), 167-172.
31. Шокиров, Б., & Халимова, Ю. (2021). Antibiotic-induced rat gut microbiota dysbiosis and salmonella resistance. *Общество и инновации*, 2(4/S), 93-100.
32. Шокиров, Б. С., & Халимова, Ю. С. (2021). Пищеварительная функция кишечника после коррекции экспериментального дисбактериоза у крыс бифидобактериями. In *Актуальные вопросы современной медицинской науки и здравоохранения: Материалы VI Международной научно-практической конференции молодых учёных и студентов, посвященной году науки и технологий, (Екатеринбург, 8-9 апреля 2021): в 3-х т.*. Федеральное государственное бюджетное образовательное учреждение высшего образования «Уральский государственный медицинский университет» Министерства здравоохранения Российской Федерации.
33. Salokhiddinovna, X. Y. (2023). Anemia of Chronic Diseases. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 2(12), 364-372.
34. Salokhiddinovna, X. Y. (2023). MALLORY WEISS SYNDROME IN DIFFUSE LIVER LESIONS. *Journal of Science in Medicine and Life*, 1(4), 11-15.
35. Salokhiddinovna, X. Y. (2023). SURUNKALI KASALLIKLARDA UCHRAYDIGAN ANEMIYALAR MORFO-FUNKSIONAL XUSUSIYATLARI. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 10(3), 180-188.
36. Халимова, Ю. С. (2024). КЛИНИКО-МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ВИТАМИНА D В ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ПРОТИВОИНФЕКЦИОННОГО ИММУНИТА. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 36(3), 86-94.
37. Saloxiddinovna, X. Y. (2024). CLINICAL FEATURES OF VITAMIN D EFFECTS ON BONE METABOLISM. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 36(5), 90-99.
38. Saloxiddinovna, X. Y. (2024). CLINICAL AND MORPHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF AUTOIMMUNE THYROIDITIS. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 36(5), 100-108.
39. Saloxiddinovna, X. Y. (2024). MORPHOFUNCTIONAL FEATURES BLOOD MORPHOLOGY IN AGE-RELATED CHANGES. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(4), 146-158.
40. Saloxiddinovna, X. Y. (2024). CLINICAL MORPHOLOGICAL CRITERIA OF LEUKOCYTES. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(4), 159-167.
41. Saloxiddinovna, X. Y. (2024). Current Views of Vitamin D Metabolism in the Body. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 3(3), 235-243.

42. Saloxiddinova, X. Y. (2024). MORPHOFUNCTIONAL FEATURES OF THE STRUCTURE AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE OVARIES. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(4), 220-227.
43. Saloxiddinova, X. Y. (2024). Modern Views on the Effects of the Use of Cholecalciferol on the General Condition of the Bod. *JOURNAL OF HEALTHCARE AND LIFE-SCIENCE RESEARCH*, 3(5), 79-85.
44. Халимова, Ю. С., & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). МОРФО-ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ И КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ СТРОЕНИЯ И РАЗВИТИЯ ЯИЧНИКОВ (ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ). *TADQIQOTLAR. UZ*, 40(5), 188-198.
45. Халимова, Ю. С. (2024). Морфологические Особенности Поражения Печени У Пациентов С Синдромом Мэллори-Вейса. *Journal of Science in Medicine and Life*, 2(6), 166-172.
46. Xalimova, Y. S. (2024). Morphology of the Testes in the Detection of Infertility. *Journal of Science in Medicine and Life*, 2(6), 83-88.
47. KHALIMOVA, Y. S. (2024). MORPHOFUNCTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF TESTICULAR AND OVARIAN TISSUES OF ANIMALS IN THE AGE ASPECT. *Valeology: International Journal of Medical Anthropology and Bioethics*, 2(9), 100-105.
48. Salokhiddinova, K. Y. (2024). IMMUNOLOGICAL CRITERIA OF REPRODUCTION AND VIABILITY OF FEMALE RAT OFFSPRING UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF ETHANOL. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(10), 200-205.
49. Salokhiddinova, K. Y., Saifiloevich, S. B., Barnoevich, K. I., & Hikmatov, A. S. (2024). THE INCIDENCE OF AIDS, THE DEFINITION AND CAUSES OF THE DISEASE. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 55(2), 195-205.
50. Nematilloeva, K. M., & Salokhiddinova, K. Y. (2024). IMPORTANT FEATURES IN THE FORMATION OF DEGREE OF COMPARISON OF ADJECTIVES IN LATIN. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 55(2), 150-157.
51. Saloxiddinova, X. Y., & Ne'matillaeva, X. M. (2024). FEATURES OF THE STRUCTURE OF THE REPRODUCTIVE ORGANS OF THE FEMALE BODY. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 55(2), 179-183.
52. Хафизова, М. Н., & Халимова, Ю. С. (2024). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ЧАСТОТНЫХ ОТРЕЗКОВ В НАИМЕНОВАНИЯХ ЛЕКАРСТВЕННЫХ ПРЕПАРАТОВ В ФАРМАЦЕВТИКЕ. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 55(2), 172-178.
53. Хафизова, М. Н., & Халимова, Ю. С. (2024). МОТИВАЦИОННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ ЛАТЫНИ И МЕДИЦИНСКОЙ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИИ. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 55(2), 165-171.
54. Халимова, Ю. С., & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). ОСОБЕННОСТИ СОЗРЕВАНИЕ И ФУНКЦИОНИРОВАНИЕ ЯИЧНИКОВ. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 55(2), 188-194.
55. Халимова, Ю. С., & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ЛИЦ ЗЛОУПОТРЕБЛЯЮЩЕЕСЯ ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКИМИ НАПИТКАМИ. *TADQIQOTLAR. UZ*, 40(5), 199-207.

56. Халимова, Ю. С., & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). кафедра Клинических наук Азиатский международный университет Бухара, Узбекистан. *Modern education and development*, 10(1), 60-75.
57. Халимова, Ю. С., & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ ВНУТРЕННИХ ОРГАНОВ У ЛИЦ, СТРАДАЮЩИХ АЛКОГОЛЬНОЙ ЗАВИСИМОСТЬЮ. *TADQIQOTLAR. UZ*, 40(5), 240-250.
58. Халимова, Ю. С., & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). МОРФО-ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ И КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ КОЖНЫХ ПОКРОВОВ. *Modern education and development*, 10(1), 76-90.
59. Khalimova, Y. S. (2024). Features of Sperm Development: Spermatogenesis and Fertilization. *American Journal of Bioscience and Clinical Integrity*, 1(11), 90-98.
60. Salokhiddinova, K. Y., & Nematilloeva, K. M. (2024). MODERN MORPHOLOGY OF НЕМАТОРОИЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОРГАНЫ. *Modern education and development*, 16(9), 50-60.
61. Khalimova, Y. (2025). MORPHOLOGY OF PATHOLOGICAL FORMS OF PLATELETS. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(2), 749-759.
62. Salokhiddinova, K. Y., & Nematilloeva, K. M. (2025). MODERN MORPHOLOGY OF НЕМАТОРОИЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОРГАНЫ. *Modern education and development*, 19(2), 498-508.
63. Халимова, Ю. С., & Хафизова, М. Н. (2025). СОВРЕМЕННАЯ МОРФОЛОГИЯ КРОВЕТВОРНЫХ ОРГАНОВ. *Modern education and development*, 19(2), 487-497.
64. Халимова, Ю. С., & Хафизова, М. Н. (2025). ГИСТОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ СТРУКТУРНАЯ МОРФОЛОГИЯ НЕФРОНОВ. *Modern education and development*, 19(2), 464-475.
65. Salokhiddinova, X. Y., & Nematilloeva, X. M. (2025). NEFRONLARNING GISTOLOGIK TUZILISH MORFOLOGIYASI. *Modern education and development*, 19(2), 509-520.
66. Salokhiddinova, X. Y., & Nematilloeva, X. M. (2025). QON YARATUVCHI A'ZOLARNING ZAMONAVIY MORFOLOGIYASI. *Modern education and development*, 19(2), 476-486.
67. Khalimova, Y. (2025). MODERN CONCEPTS OF BIOCHEMISTRY OF BLOOD COAGULATION. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(3), 769-777.
68. Khalimova, Y. (2025). JIGAR SIRROZIDAGI GEMATOLOGIK TADQIQOTLAR. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(4), 409-418.
69. Халимова, Ю. (2025). ГЕМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ПРИ ЦИРРОЗЕ ПЕЧЕНИ. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(4), 419-428.
70. Khalimova, Y. (2025). HEMATOLOGICAL STUDIES IN LIVER CIRRHOSIS. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(4), 1066-1074.